

ROMANTIC TRADITIONS IN SOCIALIST REALISM IN THE CONTEXT OF THEME, IDEA AND HERO

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Summary: *The article studies the interrelation of two important directions of artistic thought in the 20th century Azerbaijani literature. Although socialist realism aimed to reflect reality in the perspective of revolutionary development, in this process, such features of romanticism as idealization, high ideal and faith in the future were widely used. In the works written during that period, motives such as labor, patriotism, social justice and building a new society are presented with romantic pathos. At the level of ideas, the spiritual rise of man, an optimistic view of the future and the struggle for social ideals come to the fore. In the context of the hero, the typical hero of socialist realism is enriched with romantic qualities and depicted as an idealized, strong-willed, purposeful and useful to society image. In this regard, the traditions of romanticism expanded the possibilities of artistic expression of socialist realism and made it more effective and emotional.*

Keywords: *socialist realism, romanticism, revolutionary romance, artistic image, typical hero.*

Introduction. Azerbaijani literature has formed its national-spiritual image over the centuries-old path of development on the basis of classical traditions and the principles of artistic succession. Tradition and innovation have formed a dialectical unity in the evolution of the literary process, creating the basis for the emergence of new aesthetic qualities at each historical stage. In particular, 20th-century Azerbaijani poetry reflects a complex and colorful picture arising from the synthesis of the rich experience of classical heritage with the socio-political realities of the modern era. During this period, poetry acted as both the guardian of national memory and the main herald of innovative ideas.

The article analyzes the problems of tradition and innovation through the prism of the creativity of the giant figures of 20th-century Azerbaijani poetry, Samad Vurgun, Mikayil Mushfig and Suleyman Rustam. The main purpose of the study is to scientifically illuminate the attitude of these artists to the classical heritage, the intersection points of romanticism and realism in their poetry, and their contributions to the development of national poetic thought.

Main part. The historical roots of Azerbaijani literary thought go back to very ancient times, and this heritage was established on fundamental internal traditions. Poetry has always played a locomotive role in preserving literary heritage and passing it on to future generations. Poetry, which contains the artistic memory of the past, both ensures the continuity of aesthetic word art and carries an important mission in preserving individual stylistic features. As researchers have noted, the preservation of the classical heritage is of exceptional importance in the formation of the aesthetic ideal and the evolution of the principles of depicting artistic reality [9, p.16].

The loss of historical memory means the erosion of the nation's spiritual wealth. Therefore, keeping history alive directly depends on adherence to tradition. Traditions form the basis of the principle of historicity in both philological sciences and other humanitarian fields. The concept of tradition is not only a mechanical repetition of the past, but rather a bridge that carries a broad poetic-philosophical content and creates a connection between times. In literature, innovation never arises in a vacuum; every literary innovation draws its yeast from the experience of the past. As in every sphere of life, in the literary process, although outdated forms fall out of favor, elements related to national roots develop and become stronger. Thus, tradition and innovation are not mutually exclusive, but, on the contrary, act as two sides of a single whole.

20th century Azerbaijani poetry has brought the humanistic and folk ideas of the classical heritage to a new qualitative level. The poetry of this period benefited from both national folklore examples, classical Eastern literature, and world literary experience. As Academician M. Arif also emphasized, the lyrical genre has such a rich tradition in Azerbaijani literature that this heritage can be an example for many peoples [1, p. 121]. The successes of our modern poetry are built on solid foundations such as Khagani's philosophy of friendship, Nizami's humanism, Nasimi's love for humanity, Fuzuli's deep artistry, Vagif's optimism, and Sabir's civic stance. This inheritance has ensured the perfection of our poetry in terms of both content and form.

Although loyalty to tradition was sometimes described as "backwardness" under the ideological pressures of the Soviet era, our creative intellectuals did not accept this biased approach and demonstrated the harmony of the old and the new with their works. It should be noted that the poetry of the 20th century was not limited only to the classical heritage, but was also further enriched by the influence of modern ideological trends such as Turkism, Turanism, Islamism, and Europeanization. S. Vurgun, M. Mushfig, A. Yildirim and other artists successfully synthesized both classical and romantic traditions from the prism of modernity.

In the poetry of this period, the concept of modernity expressed the artistic reflection of socio-political progress. According to M. Jafar's classification, Azerbaijani poetry of the Soviet period developed in three main directions - national, Soviet society and universal themes [26, p. 26]. While national themes directly reflected the inner life of the people, works dedicated to Soviet society were more likely to instill faith in socialist construction and an optimistic future. Samad Vurgun's poem "Komsomol" is of particular importance in this regard. In this work, the author described the social landscape of the period, the selflessness of youth and the changes brought about by the new structure in a romantic spirit. The poet's work is a magnificent example of art that combines both the demands of the period and the poetic traditions of the past.

Samad Vurgun's poem "Komsomol" reflects the merciless confrontation of the old world and the new order, feudal-patriarchal relations and Soviet ideology against the backdrop of the struggle for freedom with artistic colors. The author gives the events a humanistic essence by placing the love line of Jalal and Humay at the center of this sharp class struggle. According to the poet's creative philosophy, love is the basis of art, and where there is no love, there can be no talk of a true example of art. The work presents the relationship between the Komsomol member Jalal and the bey gizi Humay within the complex social environment of the 20th century.

In the context of the tragedy of love, when comparing the poem with the classical heritage, interesting scientific results emerge. For example, if in Fuzuli's work "Leyli and Majnun" the tragedy of the heroes stems from the clash with conservative society and old thinking, in S. Vurgun this tragedy is rooted in the political and military battles for the construction of a new world. The poet, without repeating the plot of his great predecessor,

created the epic of war and love of the 20th century with a unique innovation. Vurgun's characters are not legendary, but living, real and fighting people of his time:

Later, the great poet recalls the legend of "Leyli and Majnun", which he became acquainted with through the poem of Fuzuli. The author responds to those who consider it ridiculous to write about love and affection, and to those who criticize him for writing about love, as follows:

Bring "Leyli and Majnun" for your sake,
That epic will remain a long history.
The lakes cried in Leyli's eyes,
The steppes opened their arms to Majnun...
Love is always a passing bird,
So these epics are invented.
No matter what... There is blood in them,
There is a living, fluttering, loving person [8, p. 54].

In Samad Vurgun's work, patriotism and universal values are in dialectical unity. He sanctified the concept of "Homeland", identifying it with such spiritual categories as honor and conscience, and gave this concept a new semantic meaning. At the same time, the friendship of peoples and humanistic ideals are the main factors determining the human scale of his poetry.

One of the important factors determining the aesthetic qualities of Vurgun's poetry is the romantic pathos in his work. If subjective feelings and an addiction to aesthetic beauty dominated the poet's early work, then this romance turned into a stylistic quality arising from the inner essence of events. As researchers have noted, the romantic view is no longer an artificially applied "dress", but a passionate means of description originating from the artistic fact itself [2, p. 35].

The poem "Azerbaijan", written by the author in 1935, is considered one of the pinnacle examples of our national poetry. This work is a poetic manifesto of love for the homeland, a perfect artistic reflection of the nature and soul of Azerbaijan. Here, the poet, using the possibilities of word art, presents the homeland as a romantic embodiment of the people's dreams:

The people know that you are mine,
You are my homeland, my nest, my abode,
You are my mother, my native homeland!
Will the heart be separated from the soul?
Azerbaijan, Azerbaijan [7, p. 57].

In the formation of S. Vurgun's poetry, along with Azerbaijani romantics, the creative principles of artists such as Tofiq Fikret and Nazim Hikmet from Turkish literature, and J. Byron and Schiller from European literature also played an important role. In his first poems written in the aruz meter, the search for the "I", spiritual upheavals and the question of truth, characteristic of H. Javid and M. Hadi, are clearly felt.

Mikayil Mushfig's work also attracts attention as a synthesis of modernism and romanticism in Azerbaijani literature. His poetry is distinguished by its simplicity, lyrical fluidity and youthful energy. Mushfig's romantic heritage can be divided into three main directions:

1. The glorification of human feelings and love;
2. The harmony of nature and lyrical feelings;
3. The expression of the ideals of freedom and happiness.

Mushfig idealizes love not only as an individual feeling, but also as a part of the universe and a universal value. His poem "If only that garden were there again" is the most vivid example of this romantic nostalgia and artistic imagination. This work, as a sad song that takes the reader to the past, to the world of memories, has entered the ranks of the pearls of our national poetry:

If only that garden were there again, we would come to you again,
We would talk, we would laugh.
You would soothe my soul with your timid glances,
You would make me happy.
We would open a secret conversation about the soul's need
From your brother, sister
You would often change the conversation,
You would change with me.
Once again, our hearts would secretly beat
You, oh, dark-haired fellow! [4, p. 130]

In the poem "If only that garden were there again", the author artistically expresses his desire to return to the past, to the world of loving memories, under the influence of nostalgic feelings. This work, dedicated to the theme of love, is considered one of the fundamental examples of Azerbaijani romantic poetry. Against the background of the description of sad summer memories experienced in coastal gardens, the inner world, dreams and emotional state of the lyrical hero are united in a single romantic context of thought.

Although Mikayil Mushfig deeply felt the socio-political difficulties of the era and the ideological oppression created by the Soviet regime, in his poetry he brought to the forefront the love of life, the right of man to live and enjoy. It was precisely this unshakable humanism and optimism that distinguished him from his contemporaries. The inexhaustible love in the poet's inner world bridged dreams to the real world, promoting the idea that man should not be just a spectator in this mortal world, but a creative and happy being:

The world is a garden that does not fade,
It is customary here to die without laughing!
Woe to the person who is a blackbird,
How fitting it is for a person to laugh! [4, p. 121]

Mushfig's lyrical-romantic style opened a new stage in Azerbaijani poetry. The artist's creativity, which speaks of the smallest details of nature with great love, is a manifestation of the value given to every moment of life. Although he felt the transience of life and the inevitability of separation, he tried to immortalize himself and his feelings in verses:

Ah, how can I give up this beautiful,
Bright world day by day?
How can I give up this
Friend, the familiar, who collides with the earth, touches the sky? [4, p. 83]

Musical harmony and rhythm are of particular importance in the poet's romantic heritage. The successful synthesis of classical poetic forms and free verse made his poetry very fluid and effective, and created the basis for many of his works to become songs that are memorized by tongues.

Another prominent figure of Azerbaijani Soviet literature, Suleyman Rustam, is distinguished by his innovation and enthusiastic poetic spirit. Although the outer layer of his creativity corresponded to the ideological requirements of the era - the method of socialist realism, the strong influence of romantic traditions was clearly visible in the inner layer of his

lyricism. His book "From the World to the Thrill", published in 1927, became a manifesto of new development trends and different poetic directions in our poetry.

S. Rustam managed to create works with a fighting spirit that looked to the future with hope even in difficult political conditions. The theme of the Motherland, which stood at the center of his creativity, was worked out with romantic excitement and acted as an artistic embodiment of national feelings. Especially in the series "Poems of the South", the poet combined the pain of a divided homeland with the desire for national independence and integrity. This was a very risky and courageous step for the political environment of the era of repression:

Look, what a strange fate I have,
I am Suleiman of that kind, this kind [5, p.13]

Or

Take your friends to your bosom, oh blood of Araz,
You were born from my bloody tears, Araz! [5, p.18]

The poet tried to keep the idea of a whole Azerbaijan alive in the minds of the people by turning the southern problem from an individual grief into a national issue. His sharp protest in defense of his native language at a time when the language was being assimilated (the lines beginning with the cry "Don't touch") is a clear example of his civic position:

I don't touch your language, executioner,
Come on, don't touch my native language either!
You also have a garden, you have a rose, be careful,
Don't touch the rose I planted in my garden! [5, p.7]

The ghazal genre also occupies a special place in Suleyman Rustam's creativity. He expanded the boundaries of this classical genre, enriching it with modern themes, civic pathos and a journalistic spirit. As the poet expressed in his poem "My Philosophy", loyalty to the heritage of his ancestors and the preservation of national values formed the basic principle of his art:

I have been through a lot of trouble,
I have never written the truth, but the opposite,
To the good heritage of my ancestors
Eternal respect is my philosophy [6, p. 17]

Suleyman Rustam's poem "My philosophy" is one of the examples of exceptional importance in 20th century Azerbaijani poetry in terms of both the evolution of the literary structure and the depth of philosophical considerations. In this work, the author's view of the socio-cultural environment, as well as the dialectical relationship between the individual and fate, are analyzed on an artistic-philosophical level. The main line of the poem is the ontological depths of the inner world of man and conceptual thoughts about the meaning of existence.

In this poetic text, the author, along with emphasizing the ephemeral (transient) nature of life, draws attention to the axiological value of existence and the necessity of living every moment of life effectively. S. Rustam evaluates the emotional spectrum of man - feelings of joy and sadness from a philosophical prism, presenting them as inseparable components of existence. The simplicity of the linguistic structure of the work is united with the polyphony of the inner layers of meaning. It is this stylistic feature that creates a semantic bridge between the reader's daily life experience and the text.

In the poet's presentation, the shortness of human life is not a pity, but acts as a stimulus for living it more aesthetically and meaningfully. This approach is based on the idea that the subject builds his own happiness with his inner will.

In general, the spiritual purity, idealistic approach, and inner purity of the individual, inherent in the aesthetics of romanticism, are fundamental in Suleyman Rustam's poetry. In this context, the poem in question is an important poetic document that reflects both the social realities of the era and the subjective worldview of the artist with academic maturity.

Conclusion. The research and analysis conducted show that although 20th century Azerbaijani poetry takes its foundation from the classical heritage, it represents a completely new stage in terms of its internal dynamics and artistic searches. Samad Vurgun's work represents the pinnacle of national spirit and civic pathos in poetry, demonstrating the perfect harmony of traditional genres and modern themes. Mikayil Mushfig, on the other hand, expanded the horizons of artistic thinking with the lyrical-romantic flow and love of life he brought to poetry, taking the aesthetic reflection of the inner world of man to a new level.

The revolutionary romance and poetic expression of the pain of a divided homeland observed in Suleyman Rustam's work once again confirm the social and national responsibility of poetry. The modern shades he brought to the classical ghazal genre and the idea of a whole Azerbaijan in the series "Southern Poems" prove that the artist prioritized national interests over any ideological conjuncture.

In conclusion, it can be noted that loyalty to tradition was not a repetition of the past for these artists, but, on the contrary, a solid foundation for innovative searches aimed at the future. This line of succession created conditions for modern Azerbaijani poetry to preserve its uniqueness and take a worthy place in the world literary context.

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